

Enhancing the Monitoring System for River Water Quality: Harnessing the Power of Satellite Data and Machine Learning

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Enhancing the monitoring system for river water quality: harnessing the power of satellite data and machine learning

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ABSTRACT

Accurate monitoring of water temperature (T), electrical conductivity (EC), and dissolved oxygen (DO) is essential for assessing river health, yet conventional methods are often limited by cost, coverage, and data latency. This study proposes an integrated framework that combines Sentinel-2 satellite imagery with machine learning (ML) models to enhance large-scale, real-time water quality monitoring. Five ML algorithms – deep neural networks, eXtreme gradient boosting, Kolmogorov–Arnold networks, long short-term memory (LSTM), and temporal Kolmogorov–Arnold networks – were evaluated using daily time-series data for the Danube River at Novi Sad from October 2012 to December 2023. Model interpretability was ensured through Shapley additive explanations and LIME. LSTM achieved the highest accuracy for temperature prediction ($R^2 = 0.97$, RMSE = 1.45 °C, standard error = 1.31 °C), while XGBoost outperformed others for dissolved oxygen ($R^2 = 0.79$). High accuracy was also observed for conductivity predictions (LSTM, $R^2 = 0.90$). Seasonal variables and spectral bands (B8a, B4, B11) were found to be dominant predictors. The novelty of this work lies in the fusion of temporal deep learning, explainable AI, and multispectral satellite data for interpretable, scalable, and cost-effective water quality assessment. This approach supports timely water quality degradation and decision-making in river basin management.

Key words: Danube River, machine learning, pollution detection, satellite data, sustainability, water quality monitoring

HIGHLIGHTS

- Sentinel-2 satellite imagery was integrated with deep learning models to enable near-real-time monitoring of Danube River water quality.
- Five deep learning models were tested to predict temperature, electrical conductivity, and dissolved oxygen using satellite and historical *in situ* data.
- LSTM and TKAN models captured seasonal dynamics and temporal dependencies, enhancing prediction accuracy for key water parameters.
- XGBoost proved effective for oxygen-level prediction, offering practical value for early pollution detection.
- Explainable AI techniques (SHAP, LIME) identified seasonal indicators and specific spectral bands as dominant drivers of water quality variability.

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION

River water quality is critical for the environment, biodiversity, human health, and well-being. Clean river water is also a crucial resource for many economic sectors. Across Europe, water scarcity is becoming more widespread due to over-exploitation and climate change. At the same time, pollution is adding extra pressure on this already limited resource (Cairolì *et al.* 2023). Although localized improvements have been reported in some river basins due to stricter regulation and better management, such as in the Yellow River Basin in China (Yu *et al.* 2024), global water quality challenges remain substantial, particularly in regions facing rapid urbanization and limited infrastructure (Balaram *et al.* 2023; Ejiohuo *et al.* 2024). In Serbia, timely and consistent information on real-time water quality risks in major river streams is lacking. This is especially evident in the Danube River Basin, where fragmented monitoring systems result in inconsistent data on pollution levels, water supply, and flood risk across densely populated areas (ICPDR 2015; Leščešen *et al.* 2024). The situation is particularly critical in Novi Sad, where neither municipal nor industrial wastewater is adequately treated before discharge into the Danube, contributing to significant and ongoing ecological pressure. Given the increased risk of pollution, drought, and flooding due to climate change, establishing reliable real-time monitoring systems is essential for protecting human and ecosystem health and for sustainable water infrastructure planning.

Conventional river water quality monitoring methods, typically based on laboratory and *in situ* sampling, remain the standard in many countries, including Serbia. However, these methods are limited in spatial coverage, frequency, and timeliness, which restricts their effectiveness in capturing dynamic environmental changes (Babatunde 2024). Studies along the Danube River in Serbia indicate that, while water quality generally meets Class II standards, elevated concentrations of physicochemical parameters are frequently recorded near urban areas (Durlević 2020; Milentijević *et al.* 2024). These issues primarily stem from inadequate municipal and industrial wastewater treatment infrastructure. On the other hand, the application of multivariate analyses to Danube River data reveals that seasonal patterns, eutrophication, and concentrated pollution sources are key drivers of water quality variability in Serbia (Milentijević *et al.* 2024). Despite these findings, regional studies predominantly rely on conventional methods and static datasets, with limited use of real-time, scalable approaches such as remote sensing or machine learning (ML). This highlights a significant gap in current monitoring practices, particularly in addressing pollution dynamics at finer temporal and spatial scales.

Recent advances in remote sensing and ML have enabled scalable, cost-effective, and timely water quality monitoring. Across the literature, researchers commonly rely on multispectral sensors (e.g., Sentinel-2, Landsat 8) to extract reflectance features correlated with water quality indicators such as temperature, turbidity, chlorophyll-a, and dissolved oxygen (DO). These features are then processed using supervised learning methods – such as deep neural networks (DNN), convolutional neural networks (CNN), random forests (RF), support vector machines (SVM), and ensemble models like eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) – demonstrating high

predictive performance (Vakili & Amanollahi 2020; Arias-Rodriguez *et al.* 2021; Sha *et al.* 2021; Batista 2022; Guo *et al.* 2022; Krishnaraj & Honnasiddaiah 2022; Hu *et al.* 2023; Yang *et al.* 2023; Ilić *et al.* 2024; Meng *et al.* 2024; Mishra *et al.* 2024; Shamloo & Sima 2024).

Advanced ML frameworks increasingly incorporate domain-specific knowledge (e.g., spatial features, seasonal cycles, and terrain properties), often improving generalizability and reducing overfitting (Tadić *et al.* 2024). Several studies highlight the value of combining spectral bands with seasonal or hydrometeorological indicators (Huangfu *et al.* 2020; Wang *et al.* 2022; Zhou *et al.* 2024), while others explore temporal modeling through long short-term memory (LSTM) networks or hybrid frameworks that integrate remote sensing and meteorological features (Hu *et al.* 2019; Liu *et al.* 2019, Zhu *et al.* 2022; Sha *et al.* 2021; Rahat *et al.* 2023; Meng *et al.* 2024). UAV–satellite fusion and techniques such as super-resolution (Elijah *et al.* 2018; Tian *et al.* 2024; Yang *et al.* 2023) have further addressed spatial limitations, enhancing prediction accuracy in small or optically complex rivers by using advanced ML models such as mixed density network MDN and XGBoost (Yang *et al.* 2023; Tian *et al.* 2024). This hybrid approach provided higher accuracy for oligotrophic and mesotrophic water bodies, demonstrating the value of combining unmanned aerial vehicles and satellite platforms for detailed monitoring. Such integrations are particularly beneficial for capturing regional variability in water optical properties.

Taking into account the aforementioned research, it illustrates the growing potential of remote sensing and ML in advancing water quality monitoring systems. By integrating multispectral and hyperspectral satellite data with advanced AI techniques, researchers can overcome traditional limitations such as infrequent sampling and limited spatial coverage (Tadić *et al.* 2015, 2017; Ilić *et al.* 2016). This integrated approach holds significant promise for improving the accuracy and applicability of water quality assessments, particularly in diverse and dynamic aquatic environments. However, continued research is essential to address challenges like data imbalances, atmospheric corrections, and the integration of multi-source datasets, ensuring the reliability of these systems for sustainable water resource management globally (Dodig *et al.* 2024).

Despite these methodological advances, challenges remain, including the need for improved model generalization across diverse basins, handling of temporally mismatched or sparse ground-truth data, and the integration of uncertainty estimates for operational deployment. Future efforts must also address sensor inter-calibration, atmospheric corrections (Swain & Sahoo 2017; Zhao *et al.* 2024), and class imbalances in water quality datasets, particularly for optically inactive parameters like total nitrogen or chemical oxygen demand (Huangfu *et al.* 2020; Anand *et al.* 2024; Tian *et al.* 2024). Moreover, the distinct spectral and temporal characteristics of optically active versus inactive parameters necessitate tailored modeling strategies to ensure robust prediction performance across diverse aquatic environments (Vakili & Amanollahi 2020; Meng *et al.* 2024; Mishra *et al.* 2024).

This study builds on that foundation by comparing five distinct ML models, including emerging architectures such as the Kolmogorov–Arnold network and its temporal variant, and by predicting multiple water quality parameters simultaneously based on Sentinel-2 data – a setup still relatively underrepresented in the current literature (Ilić *et al.* 2024; Vinokić *et al.* 2024).

Unlike periodic sampling with conventional measurement methods, which suffer from limited spatial coverage and delayed response times, integrating satellite data with deep learning (DL) alongside measured data provides a comprehensive and dynamic solution for water quality monitoring and decision-making. This study pioneers a novel framework integrating Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery with Kolmogorov (KAN)–Arnold networks, temporal Kolmogorov–Arnold networks (TKAN), and explainable AI techniques to deliver scalable, interpretable, and near-real-time water quality monitoring for the Danube River. Therefore, the main objective of this paper is to develop and evaluate methods for predicting water quality parameters using satellite data and advanced deep-learning models. A key aim is to propose a new concept for water quality prediction by leveraging the capabilities of the KAN and TKAN with multispectral satellite imagery. These advanced models are designed to extract spatial and temporal features from satellite data, offering a significant enhancement in predictive accuracy for river stream water quality. Secondly, this study aims to benchmark the KAN and TKAN methodologies with commonly used ML methods for water quality prediction, such as DNN, LSTM and XGBoost. By comparing different modeling frameworks, the study aims to determine the relative strengths and limitations of each approach. This analysis is followed by expandability tests of different approaches to single out the most influential input parameters for water quality conditions. Finally, the study is performed for the Danube River Basin within the highly dense urban area of Novi Sad City (Serbia), recognized as a European hotspot location in terms of potential water pollution because communal wastewater is being discharged into the Danube without any

treatment. Moreover, industries without water treatment systems, especially extended agricultural activities, slaughterhouses, and similar must be considered as another major source of pollution.

METHODS

Our methodology integrates remote sensing techniques, ML models, and advanced statistical analyses to establish a robust framework for assessing water quality. Acquiring comprehensive and high-quality data is essential for effectively implementing this framework; the following subsection outlines the data collection procedures that support our analyses. A general methodology for predicting substantial water quality parameters – namely, water temperature (T), electrical conductivity (EC), and DO – using satellite imagery and advanced ML models is depicted in [Figure 1](#). The selected algorithms provide distinct advantages for handling temporal data, complex nonlinear relationships, and varying data scales. Specifically, they employ five modeling approaches: DNN, XGBoost, KAN, LSTM, and TKAN, as shown in [Figure 1\(b\)](#). These models are categorized into two groups: those making predictions based on current data steps (short-term memory models) and those making predictions based on time series (long-term memory models). Short-term memory models, such as DNN, XGBoost, and KAN, rely solely on the most recent input data and are optimized for immediate, snapshot predictions without explicitly incorporating past temporal dynamics. In contrast, long-term memory models like LSTM and TKAN are specifically designed to capture temporal dependencies and seasonal trends by analyzing sequences of historical data, allowing them to forecast future changes more accurately.

Data collection

Considering the ecological, economic, and strategic importance of the Danube River, water quality monitoring in the Republic of Serbia is conducted by the Serbian Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA), which follows the provisions of the EU Water Framework Directive ([EC 2000](#)). This legal framework requires systematic monitoring of the ecological and chemical status of surface waters, with a focus on both long-term trends and pollution-related risks. For the purpose of this study, publicly available data from SEPA's monitoring program were used, specifically focusing on the Danube River section near Novi Sad. The dataset includes physicochemical measurements collected at regular intervals over more than a decade (2012–2023). Within the scope of this study, multivariate statistical analyses, specifically Principal Component Analyses (PCA) and Pearson Correlation, were conducted on the extensive SEPA database for the Danube River ([Fu et al. 2022](#)). These analyses identified three key parameters as the most significant indicators for evaluating water quality: (1) T which influences the biological, chemical, and physical processes, as well as toxicity in aquatic ecosystems; (2) EC with influence on concentration and subsequently pollution level; (3) DO which effects aquatic life, decomposition of organic matter, nutrient cycling, water chemistry, and eutrophication risk.

Figure 1 | A general methodology for water quality parameters prediction using ML models and satellite data: (a) data preparation for inputs of ML, (b) ML models selected, and (c) predicted water quality values.

Subsequent cluster analysis of monitoring sites along the Danube River identified Novi Sad, with a population of about 370,000 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia 2022) as a major ‘hot spot,’ largely driven by the direct discharge of untreated wastewater into the river. The selected hot spot in Novi Sad is located on the right bank of the Danube River, approximately 1,255 km from the mouth of the Danube River (lat: 46.830°, lon: 71.755°) (Figure 2). For this study, daily values of selected physicochemical parameters from 2012 to 2023 are analyzed, presented graphically in Figure 2.

In addition to the observed water quality parameters at the Novi Sad hydrological station (Figure 3), Sentinel-2 satellite imagery is also utilized in this study (Ilić *et al.* 2024). The Sentinel-2 satellite is equipped with a Multi-spectral Imager (MSI) that captures data across 13 spectral bands, with pixel sizes ranging from 10 to 60 m. These bands include the blue (B₂), green (B₃), red (B₄), and near-infrared (B₈) channels, which offer a high resolution of 10 m. The red edge (B₅), near-infrared (B₆, B₇, and B_{8A}), and short-wave infrared (SWIR) bands (B₁₁ and B₁₂) have a resolution of 20 m, while the coastal aerosol (B₁) and cirrus (B₁₀) bands provide data at a coarser resolution of 60 meters.

Data preprocessing

Subsequent to the identification of the point of interest based on its geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude), data from the Sentinel-2 satellite were collected for the selected region and period of interest (Figure 1(a)). To predict water quality indicators at a specific location, Sentinel-2 data for 13 bands were acquired over a 3 × 3 km area centered on the Danube River near the hydrological station (Figure 2); this extent was chosen to balance spatial resolution and computational feasibility, providing sufficient context while minimizing noise from surrounding land cover.

With a length of about 600 m, the selected area fully encompasses the Danube River at the hydrological station location. Once the data are obtained, a filtering mask is applied to isolate values corresponding solely to water surfaces, eliminating land or other non-water-related areas and focusing only on the site of the hydrological station. Additionally, a temporal change is assigned to each data point based on the acquisition date (Figure 1(a)), incorporating seasonal variations into the dataset described by the Sentinel-2 data (band 7). The final dataset

Figure 2 | Novi Sad monitoring station operated by the SEPA.

Figure 3 | Measured values of temperature, electrical conductivity, and dissolved oxygen at the Novi Sad monitoring site from 2012 to 2023 (SEPA 2025).

comprises 13 spectral band values over the considered period (2012–2023) at the site of the Novi Sad hydrological station (Figure 3). These variables serve as input features for the ML model used in water quality estimation and prediction.

Water surfaces are particularly distinct in the B_7 data, especially during the summer months. Seasonal differences are evident, with the spectral contrast between water and land most pronounced in July. Water bodies generally show lower reflectance values in B_7 compared to the higher values observed for land areas. Based on these properties, masks are created using B_7 to separate water surface measurements from land. These masks are consistently applied across all spectral bands and throughout the year, ensuring a robust and reliable data preparation process. This systematic approach allows for the accurate extraction of input features that are essential for predicting water quality indicators using ML models (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 | Seasonal variations of Sentinel-2 (B_7) data over a 3×3 km area near the Novi Sad hydrological station: January (left – not noticeable difference between land and water) and July (right – clear contrast between land and water).

Machine learning models

The relationships between satellite spectral bands and water quality parameters were modeled using supervised regression, where Sentinel-2 reflectance values served as inputs and *in situ* measurements as targets. All models used 15 input features: 13 spectral bands from Sentinel-2 and two seasonal indicators (sin and cos of day-of-year), allowing consistent model comparisons. Five ML algorithms were selected based on their effectiveness in prior water quality studies – such as DNN, LSTM, XGBoost, and to explore newer, promising architectures like KAN and TKAN, which have not yet been widely applied in this domain.

Short-Memory models (single-current time step)

Three models, DNN, XGBoost, and KAN, were applied to predict T, EC, and DO using current time-step data. Each model utilizes the same 15 input features: 13 spectral band averages and two seasonal indicators (sin and cos of day-of-year). DNN captures nonlinear relationships through a feed-forward architecture (Ilić *et al.* 2024), XGBoost is a tree-based ensemble method optimized for large-scale prediction (Krishnaraj & Honnasiddaiah 2022), and KAN leverages functional decomposition to model complex patterns in water quality data (Vinokić *et al.* 2024).

A general mathematical formulation is provided as follows:

$$\mathbf{X} = [\sin(i), \cos(i), B_1, B_2, \dots, B_{13}] \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = [T, EC, DO] \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{X} denotes the input time series consisting of Sentinel-2 spectral bands and sinusoidal harmonics (sine and cosine) of the day of the year i , and \mathbf{Y} is the output vector representing the predicted water quality parameters (T, EC, DO). The prediction is made for one time step ahead on a daily basis.

Long-memory models (time series)

To capture sequential dependencies in water quality data, the study employs two time-series models: LSTM and TKAN. Both models process five consecutive time steps of the same 15 input features to forecast T, DO, EC. LSTM is a recurrent neural network capable of learning long-term temporal patterns through memory cells and gating mechanisms (Rahat *et al.* 2023), while TKAN extends KAN by incorporating temporal attention mechanisms to model time-dependent relationships (Vinokić *et al.* 2024).

A five-day time step is selected for the input window in the case of the long-term memory models (LSTM and TKAN) with the aim to provide sufficient temporal context while maintaining a manageable model complexity and dataset size. This window length was chosen after preliminary experiments with longer sequences (e.g., 7–10 timesteps) showed minimal performance improvements but led to increased risk of overfitting and reduced effective training data due to sequence truncation. The output vector has three features (T, DO, EC) and provides a daily forecast at one time step ahead.

Long-term time series models are represented as follows:

$$\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{5 \times 15} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_t = [\sin(i), \cos(i), B_1, \dots, B_{13}] \in \mathbb{R}^{15} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = [T, EC, DO] \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{X} is the input time series (satellite spectral bands with \mathbf{x}_t harmonic waves (sin and cos)), while \mathbf{Y} is the vector of water quality parameters (T, EC, DO).

Efficiency performance metrics

Commonly used metrics for water quality modeling and prediction using ML models are used in this research to estimate the capability of the ML models. Selection of the efficiency performance metrics is performed considering the dynamic of water quality parameters focusing on accuracy, bias in estimated data, and variance for the measured and simulated datasets (Maier & Dandy 2000). For this purpose, several metrics are applied as efficiency performance metrics: mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), coefficient of determination (R^2), Pearson correlation

coefficient (r), mean bias error (MBE), standard deviation of errors, and normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE). By employing a diverse set of statistical measures, the robustness and reliability of each model can be thoroughly assessed, ensuring accurate and consistent predictions for effective water resource management.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter analyses the prediction results for critical water parameters, T, EC, and DO in the Danube River, using satellite imagery and advanced ML models. Five modeling approaches were examined: DNN, XGBoost, KAN, LSTM, and TKAN. The models applied within this research for predicting water quality parameters T, EC, and DO, offered unique strengths in terms of predictive power but also presented challenges that can impact their efficiency depending on the nature of the data and the specific application. They were evaluated using Sentinel-2 satellite data, which provided multispectral imagery essential for extracting the features required for these predictions. The further analyses includes statistical evaluation of the predictions (Table 1), the use of explainable ML techniques such as LIME, and the presentation of scatter charts with trend lines to visualize model accuracy and trends.

Statistical analyses

The results derived from these evaluation metrics are summarized in Table 1, providing a detailed comparison of model performance for predicting the selected water quality parameters.

The statistical evaluation of water temperature predictions shows that all models achieve high accuracy, with R^2 values ranging from 0.954 to 0.967, and the LSTM model performs the best (0.967), closely followed by KAN at 0.961 (Table 1). These findings are also supported by the values of MAE (1.198), MSE (2.400), RMSE (1.450), MAPE (11.508), r (0.987), and standard error (1.308), obtained for the LSTM. Negative MBE values for all models indicate that the predicted temperature values are slightly lower than the expected water temperature.

The evaluation of EC predictions, as shown in Table 1, highlights the superior performance of the LSTM model, which achieves the highest R^2 and lowest MAE, indicating excellent trend capture and precision. XGBoost follows closely, while DNN, KAN, and TKAN exhibit robust but slightly lower accuracy. Despite strong correlations across models, higher MSE and RMSE values suggest challenges in pinpointing individual predictions, particularly for LSTM, which excels at general trends but shows minor inaccuracies in specific cases.

Table 1 | Performance of the used ML models with data collected in the Danube River for water quality parameters

Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	MAPE	R^2	r	MBE	StdError
(a) Water temperature								
DNN	1.313	2.936	1.713	12.231	0.954	0.980	- 0.605	1.603
XGBoost	1.291	2.797	1.673	14.374	0.956	0.979	- 0.381	1.629
KAN	1.277	2.484	1.576	13.997	0.961	0.983	- 0.603	1.456
LSTM	1.198	2.400	1.450	11.508	0.967	0.987	- 0.626	1.308
TKAN	1.415	2.879	1.697	13.446	0.954	0.986	- 1.053	1.330
(b) Electrical conductivity								
DNN	16.443	448.480	21.177	4.069	0.859	0.9277	- 0.481	21.172
XGBoost	16.079	388.653	19.714	3.993	0.878	0.9376	- 1.382	19.666
KAN	16.201	420.475	20.506	4.023	0.868	0.9482	8.037	18.865
LSTM	13.534	298.652	17.282	3.302	0.902	0.9514	- 1.562	17.250
TKAN	16.123	399.750	19.994	3.980	0.869	0.9362	- 4.211	19.545
(c) Dissolved oxygen								
DNN	0.755	1.047	1.023	7.002	0.717	0.865	- 0.295	0.980
XGBoost	0.664	0.766	0.875	6.299	0.793	0.894	- 0.161	0.860
KAN	0.715	0.838	0.915	6.700	0.773	0.883	- 0.085	0.912
LSTM	0.723	0.950	0.975	6.7154	0.745	0.880	- 0.320	0.921
TKAN	0.786	1.135	1.066	7.305	0.695	0.857	- 0.346	1.008

EC predictions are vital for monitoring water contamination, as elevated levels often signal pollutants like heavy metals, industrial chemicals, or agricultural runoff. In agriculture, EC informs soil and irrigation water quality assessments, where high values can increase soil salinity, harming fertility, and crop growth. Accurate EC monitoring supports better irrigation and nutrient management decisions, enhancing soil health and productivity. Comparing this study's models with prior research highlights their improved accuracy for EC predictions using ML techniques (Krishnaraj & Honnasiddaiah 2022).

The statistical evaluation of DO predictions shows that XGBoost achieves the highest R^2 value of 0.793, followed by KAN at 0.773, and other models (LSTM, DNN, and TKAN) (Table 1). Even the values of R -squared and correlation coefficient for all the models are not very high (r values show results close to each other, ranging from 0.857 to 0.894 for the XGBoost model), the other statistical parameters appear to be within the following ranges – MAE from 0.664 to 0.786, MSE from 0.766 to 1.135, RMSE from 0.875 to 1.066, MAPE from 6.30 to 7.30, and standard error from 0.860 to 1.008. These findings indicate that the models are making good predictions, but are not capturing the underlying relationship between the predicted and actual values. Please note that DO is an essential parameter for evaluating water quality, as it represents the balance between oxygen production and consumption in aquatic ecosystems. Several factors influence DO levels, with primary contributors being photosynthesis, aeration, and oxygen re-aeration from the atmosphere. However, accurately measuring DO can be difficult due to the influence of environmental factors such as temperature, salinity, and the availability of oxygen sources. Given these challenges and the dynamic nature of DO concentrations, developing predictive models is increasingly important for effective water quality monitoring. In regions like the Danube River Basin, where water quality can vary greatly, having reliable methods for forecasting DO levels is crucial.

Based on the results provided, short-memory models (DNN, XGBoost, KAN) effectively captured static relationships between input features and water quality parameters, offering fast training and low computational demands. In contrast, long-memory models (LSTM, TKAN) leveraged temporal dependencies across multiple timesteps, improving prediction performance in comparison with short-memory models. While LSTM showed good sequence learning, TKAN provided better generalization and interpretability due to its attention mechanism. Therefore, the choice between LSTM and TKAN models should be guided primarily by practical deployment considerations, and it is highly recommended to employ multiple ML models.

To determine the best-performing model overall, we considered a combination of evaluation metrics – primarily R^2 , RMSE, and MAE – across all three target variables (T, EC, and DO). While no single model dominated performance across all parameters, the LSTM consistently showed strong results for water temperature and EC. On the other hand, XGBoost achieved the highest performance for DO, while TKAN demonstrated competitive accuracy with enhanced interpretability due to its attention mechanism. Therefore, model selection should balance statistical performance with practical considerations such as generalizability, explainability, and computational efficiency.

Models testing

Scatter charts are used to compare the expected and predicted results of the selected water quality parameters. A trend line is included to illustrate the relationship between the expected and predicted results, allowing for a visual assessment of model accuracy. Ideally, points align closely along the diagonal line, indicating high agreement between expected and predicted values (Figure 5).

The scatter plots in Figure 5 illustrate that all models achieve high or moderate predictive accuracy for T, EC, and DO, with the LSTM model performing the best for T ($R^2 = 0.967$) and EC ($R^2 = 0.902$), while XGBoost achieves the highest accuracy for DO predictions ($R^2 = 0.793$).

Analyses performed with the explainable AI library

To better understand model behavior and interpret the contributions of input data to the ML models' results, we applied the local interpretable model-agnostic explanations (LIME) method across the considered ML models. LIME provides local approximations of model predictions by perturbing input data and fitting interpretable surrogate models. This approach allows for quantifying how much each input data contributes to the prediction of each water quality parameter (Figure 6).

The LIME analysis across all five models reveals consistent patterns in input data importance. For the DNN and XGBoost models (Figure 6(a) and 6(b)), the dominant contributors are the seasonal pattern, followed by specific spectral bands (B_{11} , B_8 , and B_4). In the KAN model (Figure 6(c)), temporal patterns remain influential,

Figure 5 | Scatter charts for DNN, XGBoost, KAN, LSTM, and TKAN, for parameters: (a) T, (b) EC, (c) DO.

with the cosine harmonic ranked highest, but B_5 and B_4 emerge as strong contributors as well. The LSTM model (Figure 6(d)), which incorporates temporal dependencies, shows significant contribution from cosine harmonics and spectral bands from B_3 to B_5 . Similarly, the TKAN model (Figure 6(e)) brings similar results, with the difference in the most significant spectral bands (B_4 , B_5). Altogether, these results indicate that seasonality and short-term trends are critical inputs across ML models considered, with temporal models (LSTM, TKAN) additionally capturing the value of sequential dependencies in water quality time series.

Since all of the investigated water parameters are affected by seasonal cycles, the ‘day_of_year’ appears as an essential parameter to account for their periodic fluctuations because it encodes the cyclical behavior of the data. If LIME shows that ‘day_of_year’ contributes significantly to the prediction, this indicates that the models are relying on the seasonal pattern encoded in the day of the year. Although classical time-series models can capture seasonal trends using harmonic components, they may not capture extreme events when the measurements discrepancy from the seasonal component. Remote sensing data introduces critical spatial and temporal variability that reflects land-water interactions and catchment-level dynamics not encoded in seasonality alone. Our results show that models using both seasonal indicators and satellite-derived features consistently outperform traditional models relying solely on time-based predictors, particularly during extreme events (e.g., floods) when seasonal assumptions break down.

Figure 6 | LIME analysis ML models developed: (a) DNN; (b) XGBoost; (c) KAN; (d) LSTM; (e) TKAN.

The results regarding a few of these methods were consistent with the findings in several reviewed studies, which were also focused on predicting T, EC, and DO. The importance of T, EC, and DO as critical water quality parameters was underscored across numerous studies. For instance, *Zhu et al. (2022)* utilized XGBoost to estimate DO in Shenzhen Bay, China, achieving high accuracy with an R^2 value of 0.79 and root mean squared logarithmic error (RMSLE) values of 0.07, indicating XGBoost's effectiveness in predicting DO. This study demonstrates the advantage of XGBoost in capturing intricate relationships between the spectral bands and the DO parameter in aquatic environments. Similarly, in the study by *Gao et al. (2024)*, XGBoost was employed to predict EC, DO, and other water quality parameters. However, XGBoost's performance for DO was less optimal ($R^2 = 0.34$), suggesting challenges in accurately modeling DO due to the difficulty in capturing the spectral features of DO in some environmental settings.

Our study results also align with those in the study by *Liu et al. (2019)*, which applied LSTM to predict EC and DO with high accuracy, achieving MSE values between 0.025 and 0.07 for DO. This highlights LSTM's potential for forecasting time-dependent water quality parameters like EC and T, which was a central aspect of our study. Furthermore, our results, where LSTM outperformed the other models for T and EC, further support the findings of *Krishnaraj & Honnasiddaiah (2022)*, who demonstrated XGBoost's strong predictive performance for these parameters as well. Specifically, XGBoost achieved significant R^2 values in test datasets, ranging from 0.90 to

0.97 for EC, from 0.73 to 0.90 for T, and from 0.21 to 0.33 for DO, using B1 – B4 spectral bands. This study demonstrates the use of Landsat-8 imagery for understanding spatiotemporal variations in water quality parameters, such as DO and EC, through the XGBoost algorithm, highlighting its versatility in handling large datasets with varying time and spatial resolutions.

In the study by Qian *et al.* (2022), a combination of cruise monitoring, remote sensing, and DL was used to assess water quality parameters in the Qingcaosha Reservoir. Their work reported that DL models, especially LSTM and XGBoost, demonstrated strong performance in predicting DO and EC, with R^2 values of 0.89 for DO and 0.92 for EC. This study successfully integrated multi-source data, including satellite imagery, to predict DO, EC, and T, demonstrating the value of using DL models in conjunction with remote sensing data for real-time water quality monitoring. The results from their study reinforce the validity of using DL models like LSTM and XGBoost in environmental monitoring applications, particularly in large-scale aquatic systems. Their successful application in the Qingcaosha Reservoir suggests that integrating multiple data sources with advanced ML techniques can significantly enhance water quality predictions.

Moreover, XGBoost's accuracy for DO prediction was corroborated by studies like Yan *et al.* (2023), where XGBoost also achieved R^2 values of 0.812 for DO, alongside low RMSE (0.414 mg/l) and mean relative error (MRE) (0.057) values. These results suggest that XGBoost is a robust model for predicting DO, particularly in small- to medium- sized surface water bodies. This study made use of UAVs and multi-sensor remote sensing technologies for gathering data, in combination with Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, to predict DO, offering valuable insights into how XGBoost can be deployed for small-scale, high-resolution water quality monitoring.

Lastly, the LIME explainability techniques revealed the importance of seasonal variations and specific spectral bands (e.g., B_{8a} , B_4 , B_{11}) for accurate predictions of DO, EC, and T. These findings were consistent with the results in Yang *et al.* (2023), where near-infrared and red bands were found to be crucial for predicting DO. In this study, a combination of Sentinel-2 satellite data and UAVs was used to monitor DO in aquatic environments.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating satellite data with advanced ML models to enhance the prediction of water quality parameters in the Danube River. By uniquely blending Sentinel-2 satellite imagery with KAN, TKAN, and explainable AI, this work establishes a scalable, interpretable system for near-real-time monitoring of Danube River water quality. By leveraging high-resolution Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and incorporating both spatial and time-based modeling approaches, the proposed framework successfully predicts critical water quality indicators – T, EC, and DO – with high accuracy. Among the models evaluated, the LSTM model achieved superior performance in predicting water temperature and EC, while the XGBoost model outperformed others in DO prediction; additionally, KAN and TKAN demonstrated strong predictive capabilities by effectively capturing complex nonlinear relationships in the data. The integration of explainable AI tools, such as LIME, provided valuable insights into model behavior, confirming that seasonal variation of water quality parameters and specific spectral bands (B_{8a} , B_4 , B_{11}) significantly influence predictions.

The use of Sentinel-2 satellite data combined with advanced ML techniques presents a promising approach to improving water quality assessments and addressing environmental challenges in aquatic systems. This integrated framework provides a powerful tool for real-time water quality monitoring, which is essential for informed decision-making in water resource management. By coupling explainable AI techniques with remote sensing, the study contributes to advancing the field of environmental monitoring and management, demonstrating how these models can be scaled and adapted to various geographic and environmental contexts.

Overall, the study highlights the potential of combining satellite data with DL models to provide scalable, real-time monitoring solutions for water quality assessment. This approach overcomes the limitations of traditional monitoring methods by offering broader spatial coverage and timely detection of pollution events. The proposed framework can act as a decision-support tool for environmental agencies, assisting in proactive water resource management. Although the proposed ML models demonstrated strong performance, the study has some limitations. *In situ* water quality measurements were both temporally and spatially sparse, which may restrict how widely the results can be applied. External drivers such as rainfall events or pollution measurements were also not explicitly incorporated. Incorporating richer datasets and validating across a more diverse set of locations could bolster robustness and operational readiness. Moreover, while daily temporal variations are well captured

thanks to the pronounced seasonal cycles in water quality variables and the enhancements provided by the ML approaches, the ability to model inter-daily fluctuations remains underdeveloped due to the lack of high-resolution water quality data. Addressing these finer temporal dynamics will be crucial for applications that demand rapid detection of shifts in water quality parameters. Future work should incorporate hydrological and meteorological data to improve extreme event prediction, apply transfer learning for model reuse in other basins, and integrate outputs into decision-support tools with uncertainty estimates.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All relevant data are included in the paper or its Supplementary Information.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict.

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